

AN APPROACH TO A PEDAGOGICAL UNDERSTANDING ABOUT STUDENTS' RESISTANCE TO LEARNING

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8432232

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

*PhD candidate in Educational Sciences at the Facultad Interamericana de Ciencias Sociales,
Asunción, Paraguay (srgrdriguesdesouza@gmail.com).*

Rosane Aparecida dos Santos Rocha

*Graduated in pedagogy from the State University of Tocantins (UNITINS). Literacy and
Literacy Specialist, from Universidade São Francisco, Master in Educational Sciences, from
FICS Doctorate in Education, from FICS. (rosanesantos6026@gmail.com).*

Ranilson Edilson da Silva

*Master in Education and Communication. PhD candidate in Educational Sciences at the
Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences - FICS. (prof.ranilsonuema@gmail.com).*

Erica da Costa Barros

*Graduated in Literature from Universidade Estácio de Sá, Specialist in Educational and
Pedagogical Guidance, from Universidade Cândido Mendes, Master in Diversity and
Inclusion, from Universidade Federal Fluminense, PhD student in Education, from FICS.
(ericacbarros2010@hotmail.com).*

Lina Fregonassi Ribeiro

*Graduated in Literature – Portuguese/Literature. Master in Cognition and Language from the
Universidade Estadual do Norte Fluminense – UENF. PhD student in Educational Sciences
at the Inter-American Faculty of Social Sciences – FICS. (linafregonassi@gmail.com)*

ABSTRACT

This essay aims to present an approach to a pedagogical understanding of students' resistance to learning. As a methodology, for the accomplishment of this study, the analyzes were carried through researches in books, considering the main aspects and approaches on the contributions

of the research on the learning. The authors based their knowledge on teaching experience, given that they work as teachers at different levels of education. It was found that according to the current condition, learning and teaching are different phases of the same progressive and continuous mechanism. Since ancient times, education has consisted of disciplining the body, in order to dominate desires and impulses, as well as getting closer to understanding the most brutal instincts that have not abandoned the individual since his biogenetic transmutation, in which he passes from the condition of a furry beast for a handsome young man, dominated by the principle of aesthetics and harmonic beauty. It has become very common to define one thing by another and when the teacher demands from the student a mastery in a certain area, about a content or a practical activity, what is perceived is his inability due to lack of basic knowledge of the subject and that is where the experts appear (sic) to say that he doesn't know what was requested, there's no denying it; but, he knows something else and this should be valued, because it is a different kind of knowledge... Based on the results of the research, it can be said that one of the challenges in the educational context is not just knowing how to teach or how to evaluate, but to present knowledge in a way that the student learns and develops better and, with this, reduces their resistance mechanisms.

Keywords: Resistance. Learning. Pedagogy. CV. Pedagogical Sciences.

INTRODUCTION

Thinking about other people's actions and explaining them based on moral logic is a challenge that cannot be given attention beyond what the problem deserves and also what is known about it and, to everyone's sadness, what is known about the The reasons why students tend to mess up the class could be the effect of phylogenetic actions, in which by not allowing teachings to be transmitted, there is the question that responsibility cannot be demanded from them. In this, there is wisdom and responsibility present in the same situation.

A theory represents the final point [even if partial] of an investigation which, as a rule, is neither brief nor simple. It does not mean, under any circumstances, that the truth has been found, just that a little more progress has been made in the discoveries, shedding light on previously obscure problems and, once again, it is made clear that this light that now shines on the objects of studies do not make them decipherable enigmas; nothing more than target objects for scientific inquiries and prone to allowing the unveiling of part of their mysteries.

When you reach such a level of understanding, it is the moment in which you are prepared to build an entire scientific epistemological base that will subsidize more advanced studies towards systematic learning. Pedagogical Sciences are a complex field, even though they only have two sciences making up their list, unlike Educational Sciences, which encompass a range of four disciplines and all derived from fields already consolidated by their own independent investigations.

Regarding education, Freud stated that it is an impossible profession and, as many want to imply, he did not say that it is impossible to educate someone. The Vienna Master's reference is that the paths taken are so complex and undefined that, in the end, one does not know what was achieved in terms of results and, as already expressed above, the fact of having autonomous sciences that take education as its particular object of in-depth studies already demonstrates how much it is a process that is far beyond simple human understanding, accustomed to reducing everything to syllogisms and thus explaining what is not known, not even in a superficial way.

Within education, two instances that have accompanied human beings since their emergence are at war, namely, knowledge and ignorance. The second will always be greater and more voracious than the first and the eagerness to unveil the unknown that, both frightening and enchanting, makes man continue in search of new scientific works, not trying to prove his intellectual strength, but rather on the verge of solve the great enigma of your existence. This intrinsic, fierce and sleepless desire is what makes science advance and great innovations are brought to society as a whole.

In Sophocles' tragedy, Oedipus, after deciphering the enigma of the Sphinx, plunges into the cliff, committing suicide. Nothing more evident, after all, the Sphinx represented ignorance and Oedipus, knowledge; she, the Darkness, he, the light; Oedipus, the new, the Sphinx, the old. The two modalities could not co-exist in the same space [*wisdom and ignorance*] . She strangled anyone unable to respond, hence the origin of the name *sphinx* , which derives from the Greek ' *sphingo* ' , meaning to *strangle* . And let us observe that the second enigma proposed by the Sphinx deals with day and night, that is, one is born killing the other and the latter is superimposed on the other, swallowing it, in an infinite evolution, just like wisdom and ignorance.

Pedagogy is a science that was born from pedagogical practice, in which the pedagogue, the servant of the aristocratic family who took care of taking the child to school, to the theater, did much more for him, because he also tried to help him to become enlightened about things in life and have broad knowledge.

This procedure continues to be the role of the early years teacher, the Pedagogue, by technical training and who should also be so by natural competence, seeking to expand the epistemological universe of students in such a way that when they end their time in basic education demonstrated solid knowledge, arising from authentic and well-founded training. It is not what has been seen as the final product after a decade and a half inserted in formal

educational programs, in which they demonstrate difficulties in reading and writing and in the field of civics the situation is even more precarious.

The long-awaited and much-vaunted autonomy that is preached so much in relation to students does not happen spontaneously; Their foundations are guaranteed through contact with excellent teachers who help them think about reality without getting lost in the path of hasty value judgments that are disconnected from objective reality.

The teacher must be very clear that teaching does not translate into effective learning, because the entire didactic-pedagogical process and here already clarifies that we are talking about a teaching practice and a process of leading the student towards the consolidation of knowledge in which it is crossed by the field of subjectivity, that is, only this detail determines the existence of a range of variables that is impossible to be reduced to simplistic levels of understanding, because it is something that reveals itself once provoked, excited and not as a natural procedure, that is, it is necessary for the student to be stimulated in various fields, in order to demonstrate their real potential for learning and mastering systematic content.

Just like the Sphinx that strangled the young people of the city of Thebes, the teacher must pose riddles to the students, not with the aim of making them give up on the journey; but, with the opportunity to stimulate their states of logical reasoning and delve deeper into the issues, trying to unveil what the shadows allow to see only an outline. As knowledge advances, the need for new knowledge increases, given that the complexity of phenomena increases in the same proportion as they are simplified by scientific clarification.

In this process, the teacher, as a guide towards epistemology, proposes new questions until he runs out of what he himself knows about the topic and when this happens, it is time to direct his student towards understanding what his knowledge in a given field was. which appears limited, not the possibility of knowing more about the object of the student's epistemic desire. As a condition for fulfilling his destiny, the Monster proposes a second riddle to the Outsider of Corinth.

Here is the second riddle of the Sphinx presented to Oedipus: "They are two sisters. One generates the other. And the second, in turn, is generated by the first." Who are they?"

"The light of day and the darkness of night!" replies Oedipus. The first representing wisdom and the second, ignorance. As soon as there is a problem, we will start looking for solutions and as soon as these are found, other questions will take their place, in an indigent way, for the rest of our lives. As soon as one doubt is suppressed another will appear in its place. This is the meaning of human existence, its essence, its movement, the epistemological *vortex* that makes man always evolve.

However, Knowledge and Wisdom are not attributes that go unpunished by humans. Both are like *Djanira's tunic*: once worn, it sticks to the skin; don't come out anymore! And, when you try to tear it off, it leaves pieces of lining, which is curiosity [*a dipsomania of always wanting to know more, an infinite dissatisfaction...*] ; that there is still the possibility of achieving plenitude, excellence of knowledge, just as we have always dreamed of! But, here is a paradox, because there is an infinity of knowledge that crosses us and that extends behind man and another infinity [*a victim as much as ourselves of this inexorable past*] . that stretches out in front of you. It ends like the metaphor said by Nietzsche in his *Zarathustra* : “Man is a rope between the soul and the beyond of man...”

The new will always replace what has become old, what has become obsolete. But it is not without struggle that this will happen. Hesiod masterfully tells us the entire cosmogony where we can observe the entire battle of children against their parents [*that is, of those who arrive, taking the place of those who leave*] . And every time Aurora drives off in her car, the expression is that *a new day is born!* And, if this expression is taken in its essence, it is the night, the darkness that stops a new expression of a new light that allows men to realize their intentions and desires.

Although there is a logical discussion about this [*supposed*] second enigma posed to Oedipus as a challenge by the Sphinx, its interpretation is decontextualized, because the first enigma deals with the human being itself, someone who belongs to a *sapiens species*, that who thinks, who acquires wisdom from the application of his intellect to the experiences he lives during his existence, that is, he is a being who thinks thoughts, who reflects, who looks back in search of answers to everything that happens to him , good and bad, but which, in one way or another, impacts on your existence and that of others.

For Schopenhauer “to live is to die!” For Nietzsche “to live is to kill!” According to him, it is the day that dawns that kills the night that ends; the next moment that kills what happens... And, in the area of education, it couldn't be any different. Epistemology also unfolds in this sense. Hence epistemophilia is a crime. According to Leonardo Boeff, the only thing that a new theory really proves capable of is proving that the previous one was false; never that it itself is true! The consummation of its scientific authenticity is proven by the Academy and the body of scientists who subject it to tests of value and refutation, not just tests of certification of its phenomenological occurrence and it is in this process that knowledge is built and expanded.

In this sense, it is necessary to clarify the fact that there is no construction without destruction. In order for the student to be able to add new knowledge, it is necessary to suppress old knowledge and this does not happen without a certain level of sacrifice and without a certain

degree of resistance, which will be inherent to each being and which can also be, this degree of resistance to which reference is being made, increased or reduced according to the environment in which the student is located.

The broader and deeper your scientific training process, the greater the conflict in your spirit, not in the sense of denial for the sake of denial, but of doubt and the search for truth. This implies academic discipline, scientific rigor and dedication, concern with the very construction of its epistemological development. Knowing does not imply actual knowledge and ability cannot be confused with competence.

It has become very common to define one thing by another and when the teacher asks the student to master a certain area, regarding content or a practical activity, what is perceived is their incapacity due to lack of basic knowledge of the subject and then the experts appear. (sic) to say that he does not know what was requested, there is no way to deny it; but, he knows something else and this must be valued, because it is a different knowledge... This rhetorical juggling ends up taking no one anywhere and also distorting the teacher's didactic work and, as a consequence, the entire learning process of the teacher. student.

It must be clarified, for didactic purposes as well, that formal education is not intended to act as a straitjacket; Its proposal is to present to the student fragments of the reality that they will have to face in their individual, collective and professional career. In the natural state of existence, the rules are rigid; They do not bow to rhetoric.

Education, in its entire formal structure and, by extension, the school, the curriculum, teaching practices and the entire constructive process of the student's academic personality obey the ideological precepts in force in society. There is no denying that all the critical struggle that the professor claims to provide against the system is part of the procedure of denying reality and problems that are much more relevant than what they fight so hard for. In this regard, Nietzsche already wrote that all philosophy is a mask used to disguise something deeper, a type of evil for which no plausible solution is known.

In this sense, the entire discourse presented states that students' knowledge is a representation of protagonism, that, when they make a mistake on a question with a certain epistemological requirement, this shows that they have knowledge of another phenomenological condition, without being able to submit it to the Didactic scrutiny in order to determine the dimension of their wisdom, validating or refuting their knowledge becomes the most authentic denial of pragmatic teaching and formal learning.

The result of all this is an epistemological atrophy in society in such a way that in a relatively short time what we have is nothing more than functionally illiterate people and worse,

individuals who believe they know. This is the point at which rock bottom is reached, because the principle of knowledge is to be in doubt, as advised by R. Descartes, that is, to be certain about knowledge is foolish, because there is a very eloquent dynamism in the sciences, which expand as new discoveries are presented to the public as a result of laboratory and/or empirical investigations.

In this way, the new will always exist and beyond the amazement and fear it provokes, its continued existence is the mark of the evolutionary process of searches, analyses, interpretations and understanding of what is discovered, resulting in enchanting scientific syntheses.

TO OVERCOME THE FEAR OF THE NEW

Every living being resists the new. This happens, as a natural reaction, because the new is unknown and this provokes and enhances fear. And this is the cause of resistance. Even the development of human culture and the species itself had its obstacles, due to this fear, this resistance to accepting the unknown.

In the same dimension, it was by accepting the risk condition that emerged in relation to this unknown that it proved possible to develop new technologies and expand the knowledge base. This happened with the innovations that reached the population and that, for a long time, were put aside, as they did not see conditions for pragmatic use for them. If in Antiquity and the Middle Ages there was the issue of superstition marking the epistemological spaces that could be explored, in the post-Industrial Revolution there was the issue of pragmatism, utilitarianism; but, under this cover, the issue of fear remains alive, of the terror that can affect anyone who, out of curiosity, opens Pandora's magic box.

A very human issue is that change causes the need for adjustments and knowledge about what is being innovated, that is, the new awakens to a complex type of instruction, something that is beyond the average, what has been dominated until then; it is challenging par excellence, breaking with everything known until its efficiency and normality are proven, in which it adds new knowledge and simpler ways of carrying out everyday tasks.

When dealing with the new, the place of comfort and dominance is destroyed, leaving in its place nothing more than conjectures, hypotheses and speculations that need to be proven and refuted through a deep scientific process, which leads to a study about the object and its potential, a fact that leads to experimentation and objective responses given by it, with the scholar being responsible for interpreting the results and applying them at the field level.

Scholarly research and formal education are directly responsible for providing the spirit of criticism in the generations that follow their parents and, let us understand criticism, in the sense of questioning the modes of production, the techniques used and mechanisms used to improve the performance of available tools and inputs.

The way in which the ideology of [almost absolute] valorization of empirical knowledge, originating from common sense, has been propagated, the tendency is for society to become stuck in obsolete systems, reproducing a generalist discourse that tries to show an appreciation of the non-literate individual or semi-literate. Innovations are products of old techniques that are being debated in accordance with the need to develop work or to make life easier. Therefore, evolution is a human process, the product of its intellectual capacity which, when applied to a given object, produces a result that, depending on its applicability, causes the previous method or mechanism to be put into disuse.

There is no devaluation of empirical knowledge or even overvaluation of applied sciences and their methods. In the financialized world there is a tendency to praise that which generates dividends more quickly and on a universal scale. However, what cannot be lost sight of is that the world is a vast place and there are still regions that even the most modern information and communication technology and the global computer network are of no use to, because they are missing a key element . everything, electrical energy. Thus, for these groups, the great innovation would be the implementation of electricity networks and hydroelectric plants, which does not prevent a frightening myriad of new developments from reaching them at the same time. But, we go back to the beginning of it all: would humans be able to absorb this wonderment without feeling like they were invaded by aliens?

Francis Bacon (2000) talks about this and cites as an example the silkworm that produces a wonderful thread, but which, according to him, if it had come to the attention of Europeans before the 17th Century they could mock whoever introduced it to them, saying it was of a new type of spider theria.

Contact with a certain object does not mean that one has or acquires theoretical knowledge about it. Its in-depth analysis is necessary and this can be understood as a defense mechanism of the species *sapiens sapiens*, the one who knows that he knows, taking in a broad sense, the fact that “the mechanism of propagation of techniques is dominated by an agent strong, hostile to development, and by the innate tendency of naive people to invariably reproduce the forms transmitted by their parents and transmit them, without modifications, to the next generation (DU BOIS, 1961, p. 131 apud KATZENSTEIN, 1986 , p 39).

Changes always cause disturbances, because they compel individuals to understand them, to seek an answer and to present an explanation and a convincing justification for their application, which, as a rule, generates a certain amount of wear and mistrust, given that not everyone is scientists and cannot even take their experiments to the submission of verifiability and refutability, in which the application of projects directly to their final destination is the only way to know if it can work or if it can go wrong.

In this way, the change must offer the minimum of insecurity to those who will benefit from it or who will be directly impacted. Many things, ranging from the fear of losing the investment to even the fear of the wrath of the dead, make us resist what is new, therefore, unknown. And this is not the type of behavior that will change over time, because this represents a phylogenetic inheritance of the species, which makes it an inherent precept of being, distinct in time and space.

When it is recommended that someone dares to challenge existential logic and move towards new perspectives that meet an ideal of life, an intellectual transformation, there will always be a lot of resistance, even if everything involves just starting to see things from a different perspective, which produces, as a direct and [*almost*] immediate consequence, different thoughts, forcing the individual to have a more analytical view of what he supposed he already had [*almost absolute and indisputable*] understanding and control over.

The fact of having to review conceptions and thus destroy preconceptions that are still resistant is a martyrdom for those who admire the image they see in the mirror and exalt it in an indelible way. Accepting the principles of social and personal change and transformation that affect humans requires preparation for challenges that may require much more than what we have to offer and the conditions to face; but this is the main interest with the new, forcing the search for the development of techniques that make it possible to always go further and the identification of natural talents or those that prove capable of adapting to reality.

This condition is for a very select group of humans, a selection carried out by *Physis*, not by the limited human intellect, in which archaic formulas are the most suitable for their happiness, because this way they do not force them to suffer from having to think. “In this way, such forms have been preserved, completely unchanged since prehistoric times, for millennia, since this innate tendency opposes any change in tradition” (DU BOIS, 1961, p. 131 *apud* KATZENSTEIN, 1986, p. 39).

Nietzsche (1844-1900) already said that there is something superstitious in tradition and this is due to the fear that unknown forces of the manes will punish them for modifying what

was taught and maintained in that way for so many years and more, always accompanied by a justification [*disguised as an explanation*] for the constant mistakes that were made.

The role of education is always to show the paths to follow and not to destroy tradition or put an end to mysticism, combat common sense or other adventures that some mambembe circus artists disguised as intellectuals and daring to boast the title of professors enjoy. to exalt. Teaching assumes the use of a methodology, through which it is proposed to achieve an objective and on the other side is the student who needs to absorb what has been taught to him and then create and improve his learning mechanisms, in order to excel in understanding. of the problems posed by society.

The maintenance of archaic thoughts is always dangerous and harmful to society, because every time a problem arises and is solved, another, more complex one, appears in its place, demanding a higher level of intellectual insertion and the risk is that, when one remains linked to theories and precepts that are not substantiated, the tendency is to seek and apply these old conceptions and, as they do not work satisfactorily, the alternative is to distort the facts and phenomena until they adapt to what is considered as explanatory elements, the which means that scientific thought does not advance, continuing in the stagnation of the presumption of knowledge.

Learning to think in an open and broad way is a complex task, because it involves developing aspects of learning about how to listen carefully, even to what seems bizarre, and to make connections with what has been learned and what has intrinsic value, that is, everyone [*or almost*] everyone has an explanation that seems logical to them about everything [*or almost everything*] and, the further away they are from obtaining a scientific assessment of things, the more they will consolidate that what they presume to be true, is true. fact.

In an outdated education system such as the current one, in which all thought truths must be taken as such, the student does not take the trouble to explore the possibilities of epistemological deepening and confrontation until he comes closer to a solid truth and that contributes to expanding your knowledge base, allowing you to new approaches and questions.

The intention with any education system is to expand scientific knowledge, while preserving traditions around social value. Currently, the opposite has happened; individuals leave school imbecile, believing that their knowledge acquired through tablets and iPhones is the height of wisdom. In return, they want to change the entire meaning of the traditions, values and customs that have governed the human community since time immemorial. The meaning of revolution, at this moment, focuses on changing customs and biological rules and no longer causing evolutions in technical-scientific production systems.

According to Morin (2000, p. 30),

The unexpected surprises us, merely because we have settled safely into our theories and ideas, and these do not have the structure to welcome the new. According to this statement, man clings to his ideas just as a shipwrecked man clings to a plank on the high seas and firmly believes that he will be saved by it, and moreover, that no external danger will affect him (Id.).

This neurotic attachment to his ideas and the childish belief that they are the extreme truth, *the only one that exists* and, for this simple reason, he must stick to it is because such a condition prevents him from the heavy and savage task of having to thinking, reflecting on thought, having to analyze your own ideas and discover, *a fortiori*, that they are not capable of explaining anything or almost nothing, forcing you to have to return to the starting point of your search, namely, to the problem question that guided his investigation.

Of course, returning to the point of origin is no longer facing the [*completely*] unknown. It is done in search of clarifications on topics that have gone unnoticed or in search of elements that help in a better understanding of the observed phenomena and this attitude demonstrates scientific maturity, an essential condition for those who wish to become wise.

Due to some danger expressed in the thought above, there is the condition of being denied by someone wiser (sic) and that would cause a mortal wound to the ego of the idiot who presumes to know something about something. These individuals create [*seemingly*] logical explanations, but they only explain what they take as fact. Any ideas that demonstrate divergence from your opinions and beliefs are false, by nature. There is no truth other than yours. And anyone who believes that this problem is a privilege of common sense is mistaken; The same thing happens among intellectuals and teachers, with the aggravating factor that they have diplomas that they can claim as marks of their learned wisdom.

In the 21st century, it still remains tied to the dictates of the Middle Ages dominated by the Catholic Church and absolutist doctrinal thinking, where divergence of ideas was not allowed, for the simple fact that such propositions were made by a man of faith; Therefore, everything he said was the most excellent truth. This post was replaced by the Academy, which, dying of envy of the Holy See, only waited for its power to disappear to fill the vacancy of dogmatic scientific authoritarianism.

Education, after the establishment of Christianity as an official religion, supported by the Catholic Church, distorted the interest of forming a citizen capable of questioning the world around him, to be someone who obeyed, blindly, the dictates of the Holy See. Aristotle of Estagira (384-322 ane) argued that all fundamental education should be public, offered and

organized by the State, because this would maintain the values defended by it. Interestingly, what we see today is the State as the great manager of education and what is formed are specimens that take its values as the most decrepit and act, in a direct and invasive way, to destroy everything that society has a greater value. This helps to understand why every day the State has left formal education to the margins of its ideological investments, doing only what the law says.

Edgar Morin continues his explanation by arguing that, “the main duty of education is to arm each person for the vital fight for lucidity, as we are childish, neurotic, delusional and also rational beings. All of this constitutes the truly human stuff” (2000, p. 30).

Being lucid to face an existence that happens without the will of being, with its increasingly intense demands, is a challenge and, therefore, this is a task that falls much more to the parents than to the school itself and to this, There remains a duty to strengthen this principle, increasingly leading everyone to understand that understanding the processes inherent to life is their domain; not just knowing that they exist or that they don't exist. Every search that man makes towards his own knowledge and its mastery opens up new opportunities to bring him closer to being able to build an ideal life, for himself and for others.

Unfortunately, this is not quite what we see today. In many cases, most individuals have lost their way and have not been able to find a path that leads them to a legitimate end; something as if they no longer know where they want to go or where they want to be when they arrive in this enchanted artificial paradise. For a long time, science offered this idyllic place, with the promise of curing diseases; passed... Then they promised to end hunger and misery; passed... [too]. Now, the promise is to make people equal and behold, the bottom of the well of insanity has been reached, in which anatomical differences between the sexes are being abolished in the name of this ideology, which is nothing more than that! And, from this, the entire structural biological constitution of the species is being manipulated at the whim of the dominant foolishness.

The only thing that has ceased to exist, in these years of the 21st century, is lucidity and along with it, rationality, as they have become dangerous instruments to have too close to oneself. This raises the question that has become a sociological emblem: *For what education?* In a classic way, the objective of this has always been to contribute to the integral formation of man, preparing him for the construction of an increasingly ideal society, broader and dedicated to promoting economic and social well-being, concerned with solving the problems close to each one.

But, contrary to this, what we witness is a riot of everyone against everyone and, when there is no one to violate, they turn against themselves and destroy themselves, in the name of freedom, happiness and anything else that they want. Judge to be relevant to the alleged social transformation. They end up building chimeras and abstract monsters that require deciphering, which is impossible to achieve, because such creatures are so surreal that they only exist in each person's imaginary worlds, with the condition of collectiveness, of belonging to an ideal state of things, no longer existing. Everyone starts to prefer nothing to preferring nothing...; and so, life continues, disconnected from a human condition of existence worthy of being considered as life, or, interpreting this insane thing from Socratic thought, a life without reflection, without any causal link with reality.

Since ancient times, education has consisted of disciplining the body and spirit, in order to dominate desires and impulses, as well as getting closer to understanding the most brutal instincts that have not abandoned the individual since his biogenetic transmutation, in which he passes from the condition of a hairy beast to a beautiful young man, dominated by the principle of aesthetics and harmonious beauty. Adonis represents this, in which the most beautiful man in the world falls in love with the wild hunt, leaving aside the unconditional love of the Goddess of Beauty to go in search of dangerous adventures, in which he puts all his masculinity in check against what he wants. One day it had been, but now it pulsed in his soul, bubbling like boiling oil.

How to find the right balance between both parties was the challenge faced by the great masters and, not surprisingly, the Centaur Chiron was chosen to be the preceptor of the great heroes of classical Greek history. They, better than today's human scientists, knew that,

The human being is a rational and irrational being, capable of measure and excess; subject of intense and unstable affection. Smile, laugh, cry, but also know how to know objectively; he is serious and calculating, but also anxious, anguished, playful, drunk, ecstatic; he is a being of violence and tenderness, of love and hate; is a being invaded by the imaginary and can recognize the real, who is aware of death, but cannot believe in it; that secretes myth and magic, but also science and philosophy; who is possessed by the gods and ideas, but who doubts the gods and criticizes the Ideas; it is nourished by proven knowledge, but also by illusions and chimeras (MORIN, 2000, p. 59).

Nowhere is it written that the illusions that man clings to during his existence can be considered as acts of delinquency or insanity. This duality to which human beings are attached is their natural guarantee that they have minimum conditions for survival in a hostile world, over which they do not have any type of control. Life outside the walls of your home is violent,

par excellence; However, within your family living space there needs to be tranquility and rest, security such that you feel free to believe that no real danger affects you at all times.

This is the main role relegated to education, that of making human beings reach this state of understanding about their existential condition and, more than that, learning to manage their impulses, controlling their way of being and existing. When Freud states that education is one of the three *impossible professions* along with administration and Psychoanalysis, it can be seen that they all try to offer emotional balance to a being that, by its pure nature, is completely emotionally unbalanced. The epigraph above makes this clear, and what is sought with these three disciplines is the most coherent approach possible.

In recent years the stakes have been rising exponentially, and the result is a society increasingly enslaved through medicines, in which the medicalization of education, a situation in which everything was resolved through a magic pill, powerful enough to correct everything from a simple attention deficit to deficient [*or even non-existent*] teaching, to a process of mass medicalization, where everyone is dominated by happiness drugs, legal, of course, because their respective effectiveness has been proven in tests with rats, in laboratories [*which has an average lifespan of 2 months*], but which the State approves, since it does not want to demonstrate its strength against anyone.

Likewise, they use experiments on rats as results to define the use of medications to improve attention, and when asked whether any study has been carried out on a large scale with children, adolescents and adults, in schools or companies, the answer is that This would require a lot of time, resources and *some bad things...*, that is, a euphemistic clarification to say that everything is just guesswork, pure charlatanism. The most interesting thing will be this bill, which will have to be paid by someone, in the not too distant future.

Every time we try to reduce man to a thing, which can be measured by instruments created by a creature limited in terms of its own understanding of itself, the result is the catastrophe we face today. All limits are called into question and the command of existence is handed over to a lunatic on duty, who in the next round is replaced by another, even more insane and egoic.

The need to educate man, to straighten what was crooked, what was outside the standards required by *Physis*, was a way of guaranteeing survival and not control. If it became this way, it is because of the excesses that the being allowed itself and, as a disastrous consequence, it had to allow others more, until the moment came when it lost control, first over itself and its ego; then, about his contemporaries. It must be understood: Man is not an end in himself. It is a being of continuation, perpetuation and extension. Continued because, at birth,

he already brings the genetic baggage of his parents and his education is carried out under the influence of all the cultural baggage of his parents and the environment that surrounds him. Of perpetuation, because it is a being condemned to propagate itself in some way [*currently, the form doesn't matter, but in Antiquity, leaving heirs was an obligation imposed by law under penalty of severe punishment, if ignored or not obeyed*]. In extension, due to the fact that your influence will be [*directly and/or indirectly, to a greater or lesser extent*] on the people you live with.

The only thing that is innate to man is hunger; everything else has to be taught. And this is an inherent role of culture. From a young age, children are trained to obey and repeat stereotypes, which become paradigms, which become so strongly rooted in their personalities that, as adults, they mimetically repeat attitudes that, to less prepared eyes, take on an innate aspect.

The human being is a paradoxical creature when it comes to his temporal state. On the one hand, the time to produce significant changes during the existence of a single generation is relatively short; on the other, the time lapse between the idealization of a change in behavior and its implementation takes on the aspect of an infinite eternity and, no matter how much the values produced in a determined interval of time are taken into account, their analysis, in order to that proves reliable enough, from a scientific point of view, requires very extensive temporal elasticity.

It is difficult to understand this mathematics that cannot be determined through a numerical expression, because it escapes the scope of the concrete and is concentrated in the field of the pure abstract, far from the line of access to the units of measurement developed by a being limited in time and space. Therefore, the best we can do is make conjectures about these events and raise hypotheses around this phenomenon.

Currently, there are many caricatures that intend to leave their mark on the world and to do so they demand that their claims be accepted and put into motion according to their schizopathic will and they already expect to see changes happening, as if in addition to insane creatures they were gods; in fact, the two groups into which they could be placed, without any modesty.

For normal humans, as there is not much expectation of any change, they are left with building their children in the mold they believe to be the closest to what is idealized for society, namely, an identical copy of themselves, what they make of them. as insane as those who belong to the aforementioned group. In this sense, the school does not teach the individual to be what they want to be; but, to be what it determines, because society determines it, through dominant

thought. Here's the question: what do you learn, then, at school? Not what is necessary, but what a group with dominant power believes is necessary. In this sense, things have been maintained for centuries, without anyone willing to challenge thought, giving the impression that the persistence of that type of political ideology remains active due to its social aesthetics, ignoring that behind its longevity overwhelms an entire complex and powerful structure of social engineering.

In this line of reasoning, Nietzsche will state that “parents involuntarily make their child something similar to themselves. This is what they call 'education'. There is no mother who, deep in her heart, doubts having given her son property, nor a father who denies himself the right to subject him to his concepts and value judgments” (NIETZSCHE, 2004, p. 109- 110).

It seems strange to hear this coming from Nietzsche, because he was always attentive to the war that consumes human beings, in search of power, and none of this is possible if one does not have absolute control over the spirits under construction, capable and prone to cling to a bold idea of life, existence, being, non-being, having, power. Society is founded and remains organized through its hardest core, which is the family, and this, in turn, responds to the desires of civil society, opening itself up in a very subtle way to certain changes and remaining faithful to traditions, in other aspects of life.

If the family refrains from controlling, with an iron fist, its offspring, in a short time a dystopian world is established and taken as the *ideal* , in which everything goes in the name of anything that is considered valuable. Education, which until the end of the 20th century showed itself as the guardian of moral values, surrendered to the anything-goes discourse in the name of freedom, happiness and equality, creating, with this, a caste of eunuchs who cannot stand look at life and existence and see them as a direct result of bloody battles, in which the most prepared, those who decide to survive will do so and win. Thus, they created artificial sovereigns who speak for them, in the name of freedom, not realizing that they are, little by little, becoming enslaved and worse, they are feeding a monster that, in a short time, will learn to feed itself, coming to devour them, due to a simple condition of power, because he is the strongest, he can do so: it remains to be seen whether what was created was a god or a monster?

The school and teachers may not know the answer to this question; but, society knows and, as it lives to believe that gods are figures of good, it tends to believe that their immanence created a monster, because they taught children, from a very early age, that only monsters are bad and perverse, they act in a sadistic and tyrannical way, without caring about other people's feelings.

In the end, everyone knows that gods and monsters are just variants used to determine the same being: one who doesn't care, who appears impassive in the face of everything that happens and, in this sense, where the school and its would-be indoctrinators are fit? For many decades, the feeling of impotence has been ingrained in the minds of teachers and, instead of fighting against it, they began to agree with the reality that had set in and, fearful that, when facing the Sphinx, they would end up dead, they preferred to leave the thing alone. roll around freely and the result of everything was what we see today: neither god nor monster! Just an amorphous figure, devoid of a leader and following the flow of *Physis* , the most dangerous anathema that awaits the human being.

If the sentence has already been given, with its fulfillment remaining, the entire state of anarchy that has been established in society is understandable; After all, by hook or by crook, the noose will tighten around your neck. If formal education no longer makes a difference in building a vision of the future, why attend school? Because it is obligatory, by rule of law! Therefore, why take the teachings of teachers seriously, if none of this will have any impact on future life, financial gains and social recognition?

It is strange that the same doctrine, relativism, which was consolidated by Rousseau, in his famous phrase *every point of view represents the view of a point*, expressed in his book *Emile or Education* (1762), has as its counterpoint, the concept of freedom expressed by him, in another book of his, *The Confessions* (1782) , where he states that if every man did whatever he pleased, no man would ever be free. It would be, as has been stated so many times in this text: God or Monster!

At the forefront of immaculate power, the German Master reports that, “in the past, parents thought it fair to dispose, at their pleasure, of the life and death of the newborn - as among the ancient Germans. Imitating the father, even today the teacher, the class, the priest, the prince see in everyone an indisputable opportunity for a new possession” (NIETZSCHE, 2004, p. 109-110).

Nietzsche wants to assert that, even with the best of intentions, society is doomed to repeat its mistakes *with* each new generation. Parents believe they are saving their children from the dangers posed by the *world* and, in fact, they are. Not because they are so powerful at this point, but because there is a whole condition of non-comprehension about the evil that everyone keeps out of everyone's sight.

The problem is that it is not about the bad things that exist naturally and which, inevitably, everyone will have to, one day, come into contact with, whether they want to or not. It is the cowardice of sick and degenerate people dominated by bizarre desires and who go to

great lengths to attack innocent figures and thus satisfy their most indecent desires. In recent times, anything has been valid for chaos to be created in society and many organizations have been created and other, traditional ones, have been used as camouflage for shady intentions. School is what has served this purpose the most, because it encompasses a very wide range of individuals of an effervescent age, enthusiastic about the great social battles and, in the name of equality, kindness and social justice, an entire process of transformation of men on primitive beasts has been implemented, with the slogan that this is knowledge, science, knowledge, power, scientific advances.

In this process, they destroyed Philosophy, which has always been the great combat weapon of scientists, whether in the name of new ideals or in the name of clarifying ideas that arise in the field of human sociological construction. This science that took care to discuss the obscure [*unclarified*] points of each thought was abducted and restricted from expressing the contradictory, being left in charge of presenting ideas that have no fundamental scientific basis, just ideology and empty discourse.

On one occasion, doctor Enéas Carneiro, at the time a candidate for president of the Brazilian Republic, said that, if the school is useless, then why maintain its existence? And, at the same time, he adds that a bad education is still better than no education. He is wrong in his conception! Discipline leaves indelible marks on individuals that are, later, impossible to correct; they become habits and then vices and, as no one appears to correct them, people start to believe that it is natural and, at worst, a virtue of its own; the particular way of being and from then on there is nothing more that can be done to correct it.

A good school, which values a distinct education and does not compromise on its principles, which are based on erudite sciences and established studies, derived from tested and reliable methods, is what is needed in a society. The way in which children's education has been managed, where what is taught in the centers cannot be questioned and even the students' learning is measured in historical terms of tradition idealized according to the ego of their parents, cannot also be a place that prepare someone for abstract intellectual development.

The challenges posed to emerging generations, always committed to continuing society's innovations, building new principles and ratifying previous ones, must be treated with the deference they require. The knowledge of previous generations must be available to students through books, texts, reports and other types of presentation that do not represent absolute control over situations, if not, a light that illuminates the darkest moments, making decision-making understandable. decision. This is a pedagogical path for individual and collective education.

People realize that, by preventing the rising generation from coming into contact with evil things, we [*automatically*] deprive them. of good things, of the good lessons that would come from it. Certainly, education is given by older people over younger people, from the most experienced generation towards the one with less experience. However, education was not always based on the teaching of linguistics. It was an education based on the cult of the body, where beautiful physical forms and resistance to war were privileged. Pederasty was the big star of these barbaric times and there are authors who claim that the transfer of this power was a brutal thing done from “male to male”; However, there are contradictors who say that these young people appreciated this type of relationship, given that depositing the master's sperm in the disciple was the way that it was believed at the time to transmit wisdom.

This is a very controversial chapter of history to analyze, because the way it is expressed conveys the idea that this was a consensus in Greek societies, which it is not. The Greek aristocracy did not approve of the idea of having their children abducted by inveterate sick people and took care to create a special figure to protect them from their attacks. In Athens, the cradle of classical modernity, education was a high principle, in which the aim was to adapt the soul (spirit) and the body, in order to form a strong, well-spoken man, a statesman, prepared for war battles. .

In the 6th, 5th and 4th centuries, the *Iliad* and the *Odyssey* were the textbooks used in teaching *Grammar* and *Rhetoric* in addition to studying Astronomy and Music; This meant that aristocratic boys and girls learned crafts intended for women such as weaving, painting and other practices taught in the space reserved for them in the Parthenon, temple of the Goddess Pallas Athená.

This question that is discussed about education in the Eras that preceded us is always marked by a discourse contaminated with the ideology of Karl Marx (1818-1883), in which those who did not hold what the 21st Century thinker, canonical disciple of the Priest Karl Marx, presumes that it is essential to be considered a citizen to be oppressed by society and around this condition of political and historical myopia he produces his speeches.

CONCLUSION

Thinking about solutions to a problem that permeates the human condition and which, very recently in its history, has been discussed and seen as a social problem is an excessive action and devoid of a causal link with reality. When students resist learning and learning something, there is much more implicit in anthropological legacies that, particularly, a

resistance to the method and content and, to make matters worse, treating this as an absence of a vision of the future is offering a simplistic and ridiculous explanation for something that demonstrates that education and its entire supposed meaning for life is nothing more than a deception.

When a student asks *why am I studying such content?*, the answer is as abject as your questioning. The question addressed should be: *why am I studying this and that systematic content?*, and from this, opportunities are opened for the teacher to explain his didactic and pragmatic interests with learning such a proposal.

Much more than being frightened by the new and, therefore, rejecting it, the student feels that what he is learning is useless for his life, since no empirical situation has been proposed as an experience throughout his entire student life. . Meaning is given, felt, accommodated and assimilated by the student when they realize the usefulness of what is proposed by the teacher. In the *ad orecchio* educational model that was adopted as ideal, because this way it becomes possible to absorb everyone in the school space and speak as this being the universal principle of the elaboration of human intelligence, the student does not spend much time discovering that he has been cheated and the step The next is the manifestation of his anger, denying everything that is offered to him as a learning mechanism.

REFERENCES

BACON, F. *Novum Organum*. São Paulo: Nova Cultural, 2000.

KATZENSTEIN, U. *The Origin of the Book from the Stone Age to the advent of typographic printing in the West*. São Paulo: Hucitec, 1986.

MORIN, E. *The Seven Necessary Knowledge for Education of the Future*. 2. Ed. São Paulo: Cortez, 2000.

NIETZSCHE, F. *Beyond Good and Evil*. São Paulo: Martin Claret, 2004.

NIETZSCHE, F. *The Gay Science*. São Paulo: Escala, 2004.